

INFLUENCE OF RELATIVE HUMIDITY ON CARRAGEENAN-BASED FILMS FOR IMPROVED BIO-BASED AND BIODEGRADABLE PACKAGING

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17294312
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Abstract: *Fresh fish products are sensitive food to oxidation and microbial spoilage. They consequently require performing packaging materials for their preservation. However, most of the biobased and biodegradable materials developed and available on the market (PLA, paper-based, etc.) have too poor oxygen barrier performance. One of the strategies to compensate these performance lacks is to apply active coatings based on natural hydrocolloids that meet food contact regulations, which can enhance the oxygen barrier effectiveness and release bioactive compounds. Carrageenan-based coatings crosslinked by CaCl₂ or mixed with alginate exhibit good oxygen barrier properties, but they are very sensitive to moisture. This study focuses on behaviour and mobility of water in such films.*

Keywords: crosslinked carrageenan films, moisture sorption isotherms, water diffusivity, surface water behaviour.

1 INTRODUCTION

Films based on carrageenan and alginate, two polysaccharides derived from seaweed, are attracting growing interest in the fields of eco-friendly food packaging and edible films for their low cost, food contact ability and commercially availability. Carrageenans, extracted from red algae, are linear sulphated polysaccharides, mainly divided into three types: κ -, ι - and λ -carrageenans. κ -Carrageenan forms solid gels in the presence of potassium ions and binds well with food proteins. ι -carrageenan, in the presence of calcium, produces elastic and transparent gels, while λ -carrageenan does not gel but greatly increases the viscosity of solutions (Kocira et al., 2021). Unlike alginate, films based solely on carrageenan are often fragile. To overcome these limitations, combinations with plasticisers, other polymers, or active substances (such as essential oils, nanofillers, etc.) improve their mechanical, barrier and hydrophobic properties (Cheng et al., 2022; Kokkuvayil Ramadas et al., 2024). Alginate, a salt of alginic acid derived from brown seaweed, is distinguished by its excellent film-forming properties, transparency, low oxygen permeability, flexibility, and good mechanical strengths (Kocira et al., 2021). In the presence of divalent ions—particularly Ca²⁺ from calcium chloride, lactate or gluconate—alginate undergoes ionic cross-linking, forming a denser three-dimensional network, increasing mechanical strength and reducing susceptibility to swelling and consequently the moisture and gases transfers (Jabeen et al., 2025). The alginate–carrageenan combination offers an interesting

compromise: it combines flexibility, transparency and improved cohesion, particularly in the presence of Ca^{2+} , thanks to the formation of a more regular ionic network that creates greater film crystallinity (from 28.7% to 43.6% with CaCl_2), which improves mechanical properties (Prasetyaningrum et al., 2021).

Hydrocolloid-based films exhibit relatively good barrier properties against oxygen transfers when isolated from moisture. For instance, gelatine-based coating applied onto PLA could reduce the oxygen permeability from 40 to 600 times according to composition and exposure to moisture (Debeaufort et al., 2022). Compared to conventional plastic like or commercially available biopolymer films, which oxygen transfer rates (OTR) are respectively $2100 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ for PE and $900 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ for PLA, those of hydrocolloids in dry conditions range between $0.01 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ (chitosan, sodium alginate...) and $100 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ (starch, carrageenan, cellulosic, etc.) for $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick (Debeaufort et al., 2025; Wu et al., 2021). However, the moisture exposure of hydrocolloid-based films and coatings could have a detrimental impact on their barrier properties (Song et al., 2025). For instance, OTR of carrageenan films rises from $0.23 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ at 0%RH (Guo et al., 2022), $0.5 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ at 50% RH and $75 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ at 80% RH or from $0.02 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ to $0.55 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ for sodium alginate films (Song et al., 2025; Ureña et al., 2023).

The aim of this study is to better understand how the moisture could affect the structural and molecular dynamics of seaweed-based films that could be used for optimising active coatings to be applied onto biodegradable packaging, as previous works have shown their potential as effective oxygen barrier coatings.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample materials

Iota carrageenan (Car) (commercial grade, Louis François, Croissy Beaubourg, France) and sodium alginate (Alg) (high viscosity, Fisher Scientific, Waltham, US) were used as a film-forming matrix. Calcium chloride (CaCl_2 , MW = $110.98 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$, Prolabo, Croissy Beaubourg, France) was used as a crosslinker. Anhydrous glycerol (98% purity, Fluka Chemical, Seelze, Germany) was used as a plasticizer during films making. Distilled water was used for film surface characterisations.

2.2 Film making

Films (3%, w/v) were prepared from iota carrageenan (Car) or sodium alginate (Alg) powder by dissolution at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in distilled water for 30 min under stirring at 8000 rpm. Once the solutions were homogeneous, glycerol (15% w/w db) was added to the film-forming solution (FFS) under a continuous stirring at 8000 rpm. The carrageenan–sodium alginate (Car–Alg) solution was prepared by mixing equal volumes (50:50, v/v) of the individual Car and Alg dispersions under the same conditions. The pH of each solution was adjusted to 6 using a lactic acid solution (10%, v/v). Once the active film-forming solutions (FFS) were fully dissolved, 40 mL aliquots of each solution were poured into square plastic Petri dishes ($12.2 \times 12.2 \text{ cm}^2$). A 20g/L solution of calcium chloride (CaCl_2), used as a crosslinking agent for the carrageenan solutions, was sprayed onto cast FFS to reach a ratio of about 1.6% CaCl_2 to the weight of dry biopolymer. The FFS were dried for 18 to 24 hours at about 35% RH and 30°C using a fan heater. After drying, the films were carefully peeled from the Petri dish surfaces and stored between aluminum foils at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until further analysis.

2.3 Film characterisations

The film thickness was measured at 5 locations of each film sample after peeling from Petri dish, using a micrometer electronic gauge (F50, Hans Schmidt & Co GmbH; Germany) with a resolution of $1 \mu\text{m}$.

The water vapour absorption kinetics of the film samples was demonstrated by dynamic water vapor adsorption instrument (ProUmid, Germany) at a constant temperature of 25°C, within a humidity range of 0-85% RH. About 250 mg of each film sample, in triplicate, were dried for 8 days at prior doing absorption kinetics experiments. Kinetics were stopped when mass variation was lower than 0.01%/h. moisture content at equilibrium was used for sorption isotherm plots and weight variation kinetics used for water diffusivity calculation using the second Fick's law according to Crank's modelling (Crank, 1975). The GAB model (Guggenheim–Anderson–de Boer) was used for estimation of the monomolecular water content of film M_0 , and to the determination of moisture binding energy of the water monolayer (C) and subsequent layers of water absorbed (K) (Anderson, 1946; Poulain et al., 2024).

Surface water wettability and absorption by the film was assessed using a goniometer (DSA30, Kruss GmbH, Germany). Kinetics of wetting (angles, volume, dimension of the droplet measured every second) were recorded during 5 minutes. The water absorption rate (WAR) was determined using the Krüss Advance software, using recorded data (Debeaufort et al., 2022). Film surface behaviour (swelling, absorption, dissolution) was also observed from recorded video.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sorption kinetics measurements gave information on the behaviours at equilibrium and during absorption kinetics of the bulk structure of the films. The equilibrium in the sorption of water vapour by the films was achieved over fairly long periods (150-170 hours). Once equilibrium was reached, sorption isotherms could be plotted, representing the water content (% of water to dry basis) at equilibrium as a function of relative humidity (Figure 1). Neat carrageenan film (CAR) exhibits a little less water absorption compared to films when either CaCl_2 or alginate was added in the formulation. The shape of the isotherms obtained with the sorption analysis, corresponds to type II according to the IUPAC international classification of sorption isotherms, and it is characteristic of hygroscopic products (Sing et al., 2014). The shape of the isotherm is very similar to those obtained by other authors for carrageenan and alginate based films, having also very similar values within the studied water activity range (Jabeen et al., 2025; Montes et al., 2022). Modelling of the sorption isotherms using the GAB model display changes mainly in the monolayer adsorption water content and related energy (= C parameter), whereas the energy for the subsequent layers was not modified by the addition of CaCl_2 nor alginate (Table 1). However, calcium chloride increases the amount of the first layer water molecule absorbed (bound water for structural networking of carrageenan) without requiring more energy, whereas alginate-carrageenan network require the same amount of bound water, but alginate requires twice more energy for settling the network by hydrogen bonding with water. This was also demonstrated by authors using other techniques (Anugrah et al., 2022; Qiao et al., 2025). The apparent diffusion coefficient calculated from the sorption kinetic display a strong effect of the relative humidity (figure 2). Both CaCl_2 and sodium alginate allowed to slightly reduce the diffusivity in carrageenan films, by 10-20% according to the RH. Diffusivity of water initially increased up to about 30% RH, subsequently up to 60%RH a plateau is observed, and finally a decrease occurs. This "3-steps" behaviour is explained as follows: during the initial absorption stages, water induces a slight swelling of the network by forming hydrogen bonding at specific sites, inducing a plasticization. Once plasticized, the diffusion remained almost constant, and finally, the diffusivity decreases as no more sites were available for water fixation. Subsequently at high RH, hydrophobic interactions induced clustering of water molecules as dimers and tetramers mainly. Consequently, water cluster radius and molecular volume increase and require more space to diffuse. This behaviour was also observed for other soluble biopolymers with gelling properties, whereas bonding occurred mainly through hydrogen bonds with some hydrophobic interactions occurring in swelled/plasticized networks (Anugrah et al., 2022; De Kort et al., 2018).

Table 1: GAB parameters of films, initial water contact angle and surface water absorption rate (WAR)

Film type	M_0 (% db)	C	K	Contact angle (°)	WAR ($10^{-6} \text{ g.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$)
CAR	11.56 ^a	1.99 ^a	0.996 ^a	91.9±2.3 ^c	2.339±0.319 ^{b,c}
CAR-CaCl ₂	13.80 ^b	1.75 ^a	0.992 ^a	82.7±1.4 ^b	1.514±0.538 ^{a,b}
CAR-Alg	11.56 ^a	3.14 ^b	0.996 ^a	67.5±0.7 ^a	0.971±0.049 ^a

^{a,b,c} Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1: Water vapour sorption isotherm of films at 25°C (symbols are experimental values and lines are GAB fitted values)

Contrarily to sorption experiments, contact angle measurement allowed to better understand the surface behaviour, which is of key importance for barrier properties as it conditions the affinity and thus the wettability and absorption of moisture within the films. The surface of films became more hydrophilic when both CaCl₂ or alginate have been added. However, the initial contact angle of carrageenan films showed real hydrophobic value ($>90^\circ$) as displays the table 1. In contrast to the behaviour of films exposed to water vapour, the surface liquid water absorption (WAR) confirms that water diffusion at elevated RH or in the presence of liquid water is significantly reduced with the incorporation of CaCl₂ or alginate, as evidenced by the diffusion coefficients observed (figure 2).

Figure 2: Water diffusivity in films at 25°C as a function of the median relative humidity

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study of water vapour sorption by carrageenan films reveals typical hygroscopic behaviour, characterised by type II isotherms. The addition of CaCl₂ or alginate modifies the structure of the networks and their interaction with water: calcium chloride promotes the adsorption of the first layer of water molecules without additional energy costs, while alginate increases the energy required for hydrogen bonding. These additions also reduce the diffusivity and absorption of liquid water, making the films more hydrophilic on the surface but more resistant to water penetration. In further works, it would be of interest to verify if oxygen transfer increase are more related to the absorption behaviour or to the diffusivity of water acting as a co-permeant more than as a plasticizer in such systems.

Acknowledgments: The authors address a particular thanks to Bernadette Rollin and Agathe Pissis, for their technical support in some experiments. This work was supported by the Croatian Science Foundation under the project number HRZZ-IP-2022-10-1837, Sustainable concept in ACTIVE edible COatings development for shelf-life extension of fresh Adriatic FISH“- ActCoFISH. For the French partner, this work was partly supported by the Conseil Régional de Bourgogne Franche-Comté and the European Union through the PO FEDER-FSE Bourgogne 2021-2027 programs who invest in lab equipment.

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